

Repeater Placement in Quantum Networks for Multipartite Entanglement Distribution

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Abstract

Quantum networks of repeaters allow multipartite entanglement to be shared between remote users which has applications from quantum computing to quantum sensing. The placement of the repeaters within a network influences the entanglement distribution rates that can be achieved. However, this has only been studied for bipartite entanglement distribution and often only for repeater chain networks. This project investigates the impact of repeater placement for multipartite entanglement in grid topologies. Using a Monte Carlo simulation, network edge lengths were varied to evaluate the entanglement rates of different entanglement routing protocols. Multipath protocols were found to increase the distance between repeaters for a desired entanglement rate compared with a single-path protocol. Usage rates within networks were also evaluated, then repeaters least used in the network were removed and tested. High entanglement rates for the multipath protocols were still able to be achieved even after removing more than half the repeaters in larger networks. This could benefit near-term small quantum networks as a limited number of repeaters may be available due to costs.

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1 Introduction

The development of quantum technologies is based on the principles of quantum mechanics which offers capabilities not possible within a classical framework [1]. Emerging from these new technologies is the field of quantum communication where signals are transmitted using quantum principles such as entanglement. In fact, entanglement can be seen as a key resource in quantum communication. For example, if we can establish an entangled state between remote quantum devices then we can use the entanglement to transmit quantum information through a protocol known as quantum teleportation [2].

Most research has been focused on establishing entangled states between two parties within a quantum network [3, 4]. More recently, attention has also turned towards the study of multipartite states [5, 6] as they can be used for distributed quantum computing [7], clock synchronization [8] and secret sharing [9]. These are applications, among many others, that we will gain from the use of a future quantum internet [10, 11]. However, one of the key limitations in establishing quantum networks is from absorption in the channels creating fundamental limits for quantum communication.

Quantum repeaters play a critical role in the establishment of quantum networks as they are a proposed way to overcome these fundamental limits [12]. This is done by placing intermediate nodes in the network to overcome noise from the channels, analogous to classical repeaters. Although, due to the constraint of the no-cloning theorem, quantum repeaters must work radically differently to their classical counterparts. Complete and practical quantum repeaters require advances beyond our present technology due to the fundamental quantum hardware requirements [13], such as robust quantum memories, however once realised they will be the fundamental building blocks for quantum networking.

Practical quantum repeaters are predicted to be costly [14]. This has motivated recent studies into how to optimise the placement of them within quantum networks [15, 16]. Furthermore, there have been numerous studies analysing entanglement rates in quantum repeater networks [17, 18, 19], although, most studies focus on quantum repeaters for bipartite entanglement distribution. The aim of this project is to extend the current literature by analysing the impact of repeater placement in quantum networks for multipartite state distribution.

In this thesis, we will first go through the background theory relevant to quantum networks including the core principles of quantum repeaters, how to model them, and what are some of the advancements they have gone under since being proposed.

We will then go over previous work related to quantum repeaters within quantum networks. The next section goes over the work done in this project by first outlining the model and protocols used and then the results from studying network edge length, repeater usage and removing repeaters. Finally, we conclude with a summary of the results found and areas for further work.

2 Background Theory

2.1 Quantum Networks

Quantum networks aim to transfer quantum information between physically distant quantum devices. The quantum information transferred is usually in the form of qubits which are the quantum analogue to classical bits of information and are the basic units of quantum information. A qubit is any two level quantum system and as such can take on many physical forms. For example, the ground and excited state of an atom or the vertical and horizontal polarization of a photon.

A quantum device located at the end nodes of a network are quantum processors which are able to perform local operations on qubits. Often, these nodes will have quantum memories which are able to hold the qubits for a certain amount of time. This can be done using a variety of structures such as atomic ensembles, individual atoms and nitrogen-vacancy centres in diamond [20, 21, 22].

Quantum channels are used to connect the nodes in a quantum network and are usually fibre optic channels. In order to achieve quantum communication, we can directly transmit a qubit in the form of a photon down this optic channel. This has been done up to distances of $\sim 600\text{km}$ [23]. However, directly transmitting the qubits in this way limits the distance of quantum communication due to the absorption of the photons in the channel and the constraint of the no-cloning theorem. This means the information will be lost once the photon is absorbed as it is not possible to amplify the signal like we do with classical signals or copy the qubit to resend.

Instead, quantum communication can be achieved using entanglement and quantum teleportation [2]. This can be done, regardless of distance, if two nodes share a Bell state where each node holds one qubit from the pair. A Bell state is a maximally entangled state of two qubits, and as an example, node A and node B share the state $|\Phi^+\rangle_{AB} = (|0\rangle_A \otimes |0\rangle_B + |1\rangle_A \otimes |1\rangle_B)/\sqrt{2}$. Node A can then transfer an unknown qubit (of the form $|\psi\rangle_C = \alpha|0\rangle_C + \beta|1\rangle_C$) to node B by first performing a Bell state measurement on the Bell state qubit at A and the qubit to be transferred $|\psi\rangle_C$. Then by sending the measurement outcome to node B, through classical com-

Figure 1: Illustration of the entanglement fusion operation creating a 3-qubit GHZ state from 2 Bell pairs. After the fusion operation, one of the qubits in node B is now free.

munication, for node B to reconstruct the state $|\psi\rangle_B = \alpha|0\rangle_B + \beta|1\rangle_B$ by applying local operations.

Within a quantum network, communication between two nodes can thus be achieved using the entanglement shared between them. This can be extended to multiple nodes through a multipartite state where three or more qubits share an entangled state. An example of such a state is the Greenberger–Horne–Zeilinger (GHZ) state, a maximally entangled state that is a generalization of the Bell states, which may be seen as a 2-qubit GHZ state. For N qubits, the GHZ state is shown in Equation 1.

$$|GHZ\rangle_N = \frac{|0\rangle^{\otimes N} + |1\rangle^{\otimes N}}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (1)$$

A GHZ state can be created by combining multiple Bell pairs using a local operation within a node [24, 25]. This operation, known as entanglement fusion, takes two GHZ states of qubit size n_1 and n_2 and generates an $n_1 + n_2 - 1$ qubit GHZ state. An example is shown in Figure 1 where node B performs fusion to generate a 3-qubit GHZ state (GHZ_3) using two Bell pairs. This may be performed iteratively to generate an N -qubit GHZ state from $N - 1$ Bell pairs.

Creating the Bell pairs between remote nodes may be done through distributing one qubit from a Bell pair to each node. However, as explained above, the decay of a photon qubit within an optical fibre will still be an issue with the maximum distance for direct transmission currently being limited to ~ 600 km. In order to achieve long distance quantum communication, we need to be able to establish entanglement at large distances. Furthermore quantum communication protocols such as quantum teleportation will consume the entanglement. Therefore, not only do we need to find methods to distribute entanglement at large distances but also at a fast rate. One way is by using quantum repeaters which is what we will be focusing on.

Figure 2: An example of how a quantum repeater may be used to extend the range of entanglement.

2.2 Quantum Repeaters

Quantum repeaters were first proposed by Briegel et al. [26] as a method to generate long-range entanglement and overcome the limitations of noisy channels. This is done by splitting the length between two end nodes multiple times to create intermediate nodes where repeater stations are placed. As an example, Figure 2 shows end nodes A and C attempting to share an entangled state. This is called an entanglement link which we define as a Bell pair shared between two nodes. A repeater node, node B, is placed between the end nodes which can form shorter distance entanglement links and then use them to generate a longer entanglement link between the end nodes.

The repeater nodes will be able to perform three fundamental operations: entanglement distribution, entanglement purification and entanglement swapping. Entanglement distribution involves generating entanglement links between two adjacent nodes, purification aims to increase the quality of the entanglement links generated by combining several lower quality ones, and entanglement swapping is the operation that swaps the entanglement between two separate entangled pairs essentially creating entanglement between two qubits that have never interacted. Further details on each of these components are outlined below.

2.2.1 Entanglement Distribution

The role of entanglement distribution is to create entanglement links between distant, but directly connected, quantum nodes. This can be done in steps. First, the entanglement is created locally using photons which is the medium of choice for quantum communication as light can be easily transmitted through physical channels. Second, the photons are transmitted down a physical channel, such as optical fibre which is used in telecommunications. Challenges in this step include conversion of light to telecom wavelengths and the quantum memory channel coupling [20]. Finally, the photons are detected through measurement or interference which

Figure 3: Entanglement distribution schemes

transfers the entangled state to qubits in separate nodes.

Entanglement can be generated and distributed in many ways, but can be categorised into three overall schemes [13] shown in Figure 3. For the first approach, see Figure 3a, photons are entangled with the quantum memories at each node and then the photons are sent down the channel to interfere with each other using a beamsplitter in the middle of the link, i.e. a halfway node with no quantum memories. The resulting state is measured and thus the two qubits at the memories are now entangled. This is known as a $M \rightarrow I \leftarrow M$ link [27].

For the second approach (Figure 3b), pairs of entangled photons are created using a method known as parametric down conversion (PDC) halfway between the two nodes again. Then the entangled photons are sent to entangle with the qubits in memory nodes. This is known as a $M \leftarrow P \rightarrow M$ link.

Finally for the third approach (Figure 3c), a photon interacts with a qubit in a cavity at one node then this photon is transmitted down the channel to the other node with a qubit in a cavity where it interacts again. This creates entanglement between the two memories and is known as a $M \rightarrow M$ link. Or, for this $M \rightarrow M$ link, we could instead incorporate the PDC functionality into the sending node or the interference functionality into the receiving node as outlined above instead of halfway between the two nodes.

Entanglement distribution is probabilistic due to the losses from the photons propagating through the noisy channels as well as other loss events, such as imperfect sources and detectors, which lower the probability of entanglement distribution success. In order to handle these losses, the creation of the entanglement link, after detection of a photon, needs to be communicated classically so that the process may be repeated if unsuccessful. This is known as heralded entanglement distribution [28, 13] which decreases the rate of entanglement distribution due to the two-way classical communication.

2.2.2 Entanglement Purification

The entangled pairs created from entanglement generation are not perfect as they go through noisy quantum channels. The further they propagate through the noisy channels, the more the entanglement in the state degrades and this decrease in quality, described by the fidelity of the state, represents a loss of information. The errors coming from the channel are known as operation errors, which can also come from imperfections during measurements and gate operations, and crucially cannot be mitigated by repetition in the entanglement distribution stage.

Entanglement purification, also known as entanglement distillation, can be used to handle operation errors. The process was first introduced by Bennett et al. [29] and aims to increase the fidelity of an entangled state by combining several lower quality entangled pairs into fewer higher quality maximally entangled pairs. This is done using only local operations and classical communication (LOCC). However, again there is two-way classical communication required for this which is the main bottleneck of communication rates for quantum repeaters.

2.2.3 Entanglement Swapping

Finally, after creating high quality entanglement links between directly connected repeater nodes, entanglement can be extended using a process known as entanglement swapping. This is done by taking a Bell state measurement (BSM) on two qubits within a node where each qubit is part of a Bell state with another qubit in an adjacent node. After the measurement a longer entanglement link is formed between the adjacent nodes. This is essentially quantum teleportation, however, instead of teleporting a data qubit the middle node teleports one of the Bell state qubits to the other node using the other Bell state.

To have a clearer idea of the process, we will go over the protocol step by step as is illustrated in Figure 4. In the first row, five nodes (A-E) share entanglement links between them. For example, the qubits in node A and node C share a Bell state with qubits B_1 and B_2 of node B respectively, such as $|\Psi^+\rangle_{AB_1}$ and $|\Psi^+\rangle_{CB_2}$. Then in the second row, node B performs a BSM locally on its qubits, with a potential outcome of $|\Psi^+\rangle_{B_1B_2}$, projecting the qubits held at node A and node C into the normalised state shown in Equation 2.

$$\langle\Psi^+|_{B_1B_2}|\Psi^+\rangle_{AB_1}|\Psi^+\rangle_{CB_2} = |\Psi^+\rangle_{AC} \quad (2)$$

For the other three possible outcomes from the BSM, a correction operation will need to be applied to recover the correct state. This is done using local operations on

Figure 4: Illustration of entanglement swapping in order to generate an entanglement link between two end nodes. The end nodes contain one qubit and repeater nodes contain two qubits used to form entanglement links. After the swapping operation has been completed on a repeater the qubits used for it are now free.

one of the qubits at node A or C after node B communicates the BSM result through classical communication. The final result is a Bell state, and thus entanglement, between the qubits in node A and C completing the entanglement swap step. It should be noted, the resulting longer range entanglement pair created will be of lower fidelity. Entanglement swapping also happens at node D creating an entanglement link between nodes C and E. Finally, in the last row, node C performs a swap creating entanglement between the end nodes A and E. This procedure can in principle be repeated recursively in order to create the long-range entanglement required.

2.3 Quantum Repeater Model

We can now add all the components together to see how quantum repeaters work as a whole. First, after splitting up the distance between the end nodes with intermediate repeater nodes, multiple entanglement links are generated between all the adjacent nodes. Those links are then purified a number of times to create high fidelity pairs. Afterwards, links twice as long are produced using entanglement swapping if the repeater stations are spaced evenly. This concludes the first round. In the second round, the newly formed longer links are again purified until a desired fidelity is achieved, and then neighboring links are combined with entanglement swapping. This process continues for the required number of rounds until entanglement is generated between the end repeater nodes.

Figure 5: Van Meter et al. protocol demonstrating layer interactions for a line of five quantum repeater nodes. The layers represent the repeater protocols: physical entanglement (PE), entanglement control (EC), purification control (PC), entanglement swapping control (ESC), and application (APP). The wavy lines represent entanglement links and the straight lines correspond to classical communication. Image taken from [31]. All rights belong to the respective authors ©2009 IEEE.

A quantum repeater should be able to perform all the steps outlined above. In order to model a quantum repeater within a network, although there are many hardware components involved, we can reduce them to model just the memories, channels and interactions among them [27]. Reducing repeaters to a simple model will allow for fast and easily modifiable simulations but lowers accuracy in the results as details on timings and fidelity of the quantum states are lost [30]. We assume the entanglement links generated are $M \rightarrow M$ links since this is the simplest model of entanglement distribution and there are no differences between the type of entanglement links once established. All nodes within a repeater network are often referred to as repeaters but they can be divided into three categories if needed, namely: end nodes (quantum processors) with one network connection, repeaters with two connections, and routers or switches, which are able to direct the signal to a selected neighbouring node, with three or more connections.

It is useful to summarise this abstraction of repeaters into a protocol to be used for quantum networks. An example can be seen in Figure 5 which shows a quantum internet session architecture [31], [32]. The quantum repeater protocols are split up into layers with the only quantum part corresponding to the bottom physical layer. There are alternative models to the quantum internet protocol stack not detailed here [33]. The example from Figure 5 and the components of repeaters previously presented is based on a type of repeater known as a purify-and-swap based repeater. This type belongs to the first generation of quantum repeaters. We will see in the next section on repeater advancements, that there are other types of repeaters that

have been proposed which overcome some of the major bottlenecks discussed with this type of repeater.

2.4 Quantum Repeater Advancements

2.4.1 Quantum Repeater Generations

Since its first proposal, new quantum repeater schemes have been suggested which can be categorized into three generations from the way that they deal with errors [13]. The first generation, which is based on purification and swapping protocols as outlined above, is limited by two-way classical communication of the end nodes during purification. Second generation repeaters use quantum error correction (QEC) instead of purification to deal with operation errors. QEC is deterministic and therefore only requires one-way classical communication. Finally the third generation uses QEC in the entanglement generation step as well, dealing with both operation and loss errors with deterministic methods. This would now be similar to a classical repeater set up where all the classical communication travels in one direction along with the quantum information.

The second generation removes the bottleneck created from heralded purification compared with the first generation and eases the requirement of the quantum memories since communication is only required between adjacent nodes. The third generation is the fastest system with no quantum memory requirements however it requires much more advanced technology since the quantum information is sent through the channel using a logical qubit and so if the qubit is lost there is no way to recover the information. A detailed comparison of the three generations can be found here [34].

2.4.2 Experimental Progress

As the later generations of quantum repeaters require more advanced technology, current experimental work is focused on the first generation. For example, a recent (2021) experimental breakthrough in atomic ensembles and linear optics demonstrated heralded entanglement between quantum memories [35]. Another development came from a Dutch research group [36] where they successfully built a three-node quantum network demonstrating multipartite state entanglement generation and then also demonstrated entanglement swapping. All the components of quantum repeaters are being actively researched and will contribute to the realization of full-scale quantum repeaters, however, a fully functional quantum repeater is not yet available.

3 Previous Work

Previous work on the impact of repeaters in quantum networks relevant to this project can be separated into the study of entanglement routing protocols and optimisation of repeater placement.

3.1 Entanglement Routing

Routing in quantum networks involves selecting the optimal path for distributing entanglement in a network of repeaters based on criteria such as maximising the entanglement rate [37]. One of the earliest works is from Van Meter et al. [38] who adapted Dijkstra’s algorithm to select the shortest path (SP) for distributing bipartite entanglement between two users. For distributing multipartite entanglement using a SP protocol, one method is to find the shortest path to generate Bell pairs between a central node and each user [39]. Then once all Bell pairs are generated, the central node can perform fusion to generate the multipartite state.

Instead of single path routing, rates of entanglement for bipartite state distribution can be improved by using multiple paths over certain timesteps Pant et al. [40]. This was then extended for multipartite state distribution [18], where using multipath routing exponentially increases the entanglement rate for grid topologies compared with a SP protocol. Although the studies above analyse more complex repeater networks, they all assume full repeater capabilities in the nodes. More realistic networks of repeaters may include node failures or limits on the placement of repeaters which would be important to include in the routing algorithms proposed.

3.2 Repeater Placement

The placement of repeaters in a quantum network will affect entanglement rates. One study [15] specifically looks at including the number and distances between repeaters in their routing metric for bipartite state distribution in linear topologies. Their results showed that repeaters need to be placed at optimal distances to increase entanglement rate rather than increasing the number of repeaters blindly. This confirms the importance of repeater placement, although, the study does not take into account noise from factors such as decoherence times. Another study [19] also estimated how many repeaters to use when establishing a quantum network. They explored this by applying their genetic algorithm, which optimizes entanglement generation and distribution, to a chain of equally spaced nodes and varied the number of repeaters. However, the work done in these studies only looks at bipartite

distribution in repeater chains rather than more complex topologies.

Finally, Rabbie et al. [16] also looks at the problem of repeater placement by redefining it as an optimisation problem. They use integer linear programming to select the positions of a minimum number of repeaters on an existing network topology, as well as randomly generated ones, in order to distribute bipartite entanglement between any pair of end nodes at a defined minimum rate. Although due to the scaling of the ILP method, which in general requires exponentially increasing times to solve, their results are only applicable for small networks up to 100 nodes.

3.3 Contribution

A common theme throughout the literature is the focus on bipartite state distribution in quantum networks with linear topologies. However, realistic quantum networks may require more complex topologies with applications that use multipartite states. Therefore, this project will analyse the impact of repeater placement on multipartite states in quantum networks through varying the distances between and number of repeaters. In particular, we will use repeater usage to optimize repeater placement which has not been seen in the literature. This work will build upon the work from Sutcliffe et al. [18], where every node is assumed to be equipped with a quantum repeater, and add to the analysis already done for optimising routing and repeater placement.

4 Impact of Repeater Placement

This project examines the impact of repeater placement in a quantum network for the creation of multipartite entanglement. In particular, we consider the distribution of a GHZ state between a chosen set of users. We will first look at how changing the length of the edge connecting adjacent repeaters affects the overall entanglement rate. Then, we will evaluate the usage of each repeater in creating the GHZ state. Finally, using the previous results, we will analyse the entanglement rates for networks where the least used repeaters are removed.

4.1 Model

The quantum network is modelled as an undirected graph $G(V,E)$ where V is a set of nodes and E is the set of edges. The nodes represent quantum repeaters where each has one quantum memory per edge, and can perform local operations and classical communication (LOCC). This includes performing entanglement distribution

to form entanglement links across their adjacent edges, entanglement swapping, and fusion. Purification is not modelled here, rather a parameter for the probability of entanglement link generation (p_e) is used.

The edges represent the quantum channels, and in our case fibre optics, that connect the repeater nodes. Entanglement links are generated along every edge with the constraint that one entanglement link can be generated per edge. As well as the entanglement link generation parameter, we also have a parameter Q_c to model decoherence in the nodes. As the network temporally evolves in discrete timeslots T_{slot} , the decoherence is defined through a cut-off time T_c where $Q_c = T_c/T_{slot}$. In this project we only look at grid topologies so that we can focus on the impact of the edge lengths by keeping them all the same. We also only place users as the central and corner nodes. These are chosen since the central node will increase the rate of entanglement generation whilst the corners correspond to the convex hull of the graph which encompasses the whole area. Fixing the users in this way is motivated by the assumption that any nodes outside of this area would not be significant and that the first quantum networks would have a limited number of users [16].

As mentioned previously, this project extends the work done in this study [18]. Three different protocols are used to distribute a GHZ state between the selected users. Within a timeslot, the protocols perform entanglement link distribution, routing and GHZ state generation (if valid). Multiple timeslots are used under The details of these protocols are explained in the following section. The protocols are evaluated using entanglement rate (ER) which is a measure of the average number of GHZ states successfully generated per timeslot (GHZ/T_{slot}). The code is written in Python and uses the NetworkX package for creating the network graphs. The original code from [18] was sourced from Github and a link to the updated code used for this project is in Appendix A.

4.2 Routing Protocols

In order to generate the GHZ state, the three protocols from [18] are examined. Within a timeslot, the protocols perform entanglement link distribution, routing and GHZ state generation when possible. For our case, given a grid graph G , we want to create a 5 qubit GHZ state between users in S which are the corner and centre nodes. GHZ state generation is attempted up to a given number of timeslots. This then may be repeated for multiple repetitions of the algorithms given below.

The first is SP (shortest path), described in Algorithm 1, which pre-computes the shortest path between the central node (V_0) and other users using the function `getStar`. In our case the centre node is also a user but this does not have to be

Algorithm 1 SP protocol

```
1: function SP( $G, S$ ) ▷ User nodes  $V_i \in S$ 
2:    $V_c \leftarrow V_0$  ▷ Centre node
3:    $S' \leftarrow \{V_i \in S \mid i > 0\}$  ▷ Set of users not including centre node
4:    $J \leftarrow \text{getStar}(G, V_c, S')$  ▷ Get shortest path between centre node and other users
5:    $\text{hasGHZ} \leftarrow \mathbf{False}$ 
6:   while not  $\text{hasGHZ}$  do
7:      $\text{simulateEntanglement}(J)$ 
8:      $J' \leftarrow \text{getEntanglementSubgraph}(J)$ 
9:     for  $V_i \in S'$  do
10:      if not  $\text{hasBellPair}(J, V_c, V_i)$  and  $\text{hasPath}(J', V_c, V_i)$  then
11:         $\text{path} \leftarrow \text{getShortestPath}(J', V_c, V_i)$ 
12:         $\text{generateBellPair}(J, \text{path}, V_c, V_i)$  ▷ Perform entanglement swapping at
        nodes along given path
13:         $J' \leftarrow \text{updateEntanglementSubgraph}(J)$ 
14:      end if
15:    end for
16:    if  $\text{hasAllBellPairs}(V_c, S')$  then
17:       $\text{generateGHZ}(J, V_c, S')$  ▷ Perform fusion at centre node
18:       $\text{hasGHZ} \leftarrow \mathbf{True}$ 
19:    end if
20:  end while
21: end function
```

the case in general. Entanglement links are generated along the edges of the pre-calculated path and a subgraph J' made up only of the edges with entanglement links is created (lines 7-8). If there is a route from the centre node to a corner node in J' , then a Bell pair can be created. Once there are Bell pairs for each corner node, the centre node uses fusion to create the desired GHZ state. This routing solution is shown in Figure 6. It should be noted that the Bell pairs can be created at different timeslots with their decoherence being simulated in the entanglement simulation step (line 7).

The second algorithm is multipath greedy (MP-G), which is a generalised multipath version of the SP protocol. As shown in Algorithm 2, it is very similar to SP. However, instead of pre-computing the shortest path, entanglement links are generated along every edge first. Then from the entanglement subgraph G' , if there are viable paths, Bell pairs are created between the centre node and other users (in set S'). Again, once all Bell pairs have been formed the GHZ state can be created

Figure 6: Example execution of the three protocols studied for a given 5x5 graph G . For the shortest path (SP), entanglement links are only generated on the edges of pre-calculated path. For the multipath protocols (MP-G and MP-C), entanglement links are generated on all edges before a routing solution is found.

Algorithm 2 MP-G protocol

```

1: function MP-G( $G, S$ ) ▷ User nodes  $V_i \in S$ 
2:    $V_c \leftarrow V_0$  ▷ Centre node
3:    $S' \leftarrow \{V_i \in S \mid i > 0\}$  ▷ Set of users not including centre node
4:    $hasGHZ \leftarrow \mathbf{False}$ 
5:   while not  $hasGHZ$  do
6:      $simulateEntanglement(G)$ 
7:      $G' \leftarrow getEntanglementSubgraph(G)$ 
8:     for  $V_i \in S'$  do
9:       if not  $hasBellPair(G, V_c, V_i)$  and  $hasPath(G', V_c, V_i)$  then
10:         $path \leftarrow getShortestPath(G', V_c, V_i)$ 
11:         $generateBellPair(G, path, V_c, V_i)$  ▷ Perform entanglement swapping at
           nodes along given path
12:         $G' \leftarrow updateEntanglementSubgraph(G)$ 
13:      end if
14:    end for
15:    if  $hasAllBellPairs(V_c, S')$  then
16:       $generateGHZ(J, V_c, S')$  ▷ Perform fusion at centre node
17:       $hasGHZ \leftarrow \mathbf{True}$ 
18:    end if
19:  end while
20: end function

```

through fusion in the centre node (line 17). In Figure 6, we can see that this protocol is not confined to a set path and the path the routing solution takes is only

computed after the global entanglement link state information is known.

Algorithm 3 MP-C protocol

```

1: function MP-C( $G, S$ ) ▷ User nodes  $V_i \in S$ 
2:    $hasGHZ \leftarrow \mathbf{False}$ 
3:   while not  $hasGHZ$  do
4:      $simulateEntanglement(G)$ 
5:      $G' \leftarrow getEntanglementSubgraph(G)$ 
6:     if  $hasConnectingTree(G', S)$  then
7:        $K \leftarrow getSteinerTree(G', S)$ 
8:        $generateBellPairs(K, S)$  ▷ Perform entanglement swapping at required
nodes along tree
9:        $generateGHZ(K, S)$  ▷ Perform fusion at required nodes
10:       $hasGHZ \leftarrow \mathbf{True}$ 
11:    end if
12:  end while
13: end function

```

Finally, MP-C (multipath cooperative) is described in Algorithm 3. Again, entanglement link generation is attempted on every edge, however the algorithm connects all users with a Steiner Tree before then performing entanglement swapping and fusion to create the GHZ state. Entanglement swapping is performed at any node along the tree if it has 2 edges and it is not a user. This will create Bell pairs connecting all the users. Then, entanglement fusion operations are performed at the user nodes with 2 or more edges or nodes which have 3 or more edges to create the required GHZ state.

4.3 Impact of Varying Edge Length

We first looked at varying the distance between repeaters, i.e. changing the edge length in the network, to analyse how this affects ER. Then, we did a sweep of parameters related to the decoherence and the probability of entanglement, as well as looking at the number of entanglement links used to generate the GHZ state which helps explain some of our results. Finally, larger grid sizes were looked at.

4.3.1 Method

In order to add length to the model, where now the graph $G(V, E)$ is weighted with its edge length, a length attribute was added to the edges that was able to be varied. Therefore, the entanglement probability now depends on length with it modelled as

$p_e = p_{op} \times p_{ph}$ where p_{ph} is probability of transmission of the photonic qubit in the channel and p_{op} is the probability due to imperfect operations during entanglement distribution. The transmission probability is defined as $p_{ph} = 10^{-0.2L/10}$ for a length L in km and a loss of 0.2dB/km. The length L of the edges is assumed to be equal for all edges in the network.

Another performance metric considered was the average number of entanglement links required to successfully generate a GHZ state between N users. This was calculated by counting the total number of entanglement links used during the entanglement swapping step in each protocol and dividing by the total number of repetitions at the end of the simulation, where one repetition is defined as one attempt at generating the GHZ state within a given number of timeslots.

4.3.2 Results and Discussion

For all the following results, a Monte Carlo simulation was used where it was ran for 200 repetitions using up to 1000 timeslots for each repetition. This was chosen to achieve significant results, such as an ER up to 10^{-4} , whilst within the limitations of the hardware used.

The ER was evaluated for each protocol (SP, MP-G, MP-C) against the edge length in a 5x5 grid with 5 users where $Q_c = 1$ and $p_{op} = 1$. That is, an entanglement link only lasts for one timeslot ($Q_c = 1$) and the entanglement link generation probability p_e is only affected by loss in the channel since there are no operational errors $p_{op} = 1$. The results are shown in Figure 7. In the figure, the vertical axis shows the entanglement rate in number of successful GHZ states per timeslot whereas the horizontal axis shows the length of edges between adjacent repeaters. In the horizontal axis, two extra values are added: the photon transmission probability (p_{ph}) and the entanglement link generation probability (p_e) corresponding to each edge length value.

The results shown in Figure 7 show that the MP-C protocol has the highest ER for all edge lengths followed by MP-G and then SP. This is an expected result as it follows from the results from [18] where MP-C, followed by MP-G, had the best performance for a given entanglement link generation probability. This translates to being able to place repeaters further apart to achieve the same rates, for example, for an ER of 10^{-1} , repeaters will be needed around every 13km for MP-C, 7km for MP-G, and 3km for SP.

With the same setup of a 5x5 grid and $p_{op} = 1$, a sweep of Q_c was done as shown in Figure 8, where the same axes of Figure 7 were used with edge length increased to full range of 160km. $Q_c \gg 1$ represents decoherence not playing a role as Q_c

Figure 7: ER against edge length for 5x5 grid.

will be higher than the number of timeslots used. Again with the same setup, the number of entanglement links required was found for a few of the Q_c cases to help analyse the behaviour. The results are shown in Figure 9.

When we increase the coherence times, as in Figure 8, all three protocols follow a shape where their ER decreases linearly with increasing edge length then curves into a sharper fall. This curve moves to the right approximately at an ER of $1/Q_c$, for example, at $Q_c = 10$ the curve begins at 10^{-1} ER and at $Q_c = 100$ the curve begins at 10^{-2} ER. Comparing $Q_c = 10$ and $Q_c = 1$, there is an improvement in ER for all protocols, for example, for an ER of 10^{-1} , repeaters would be needed approximately every 40km for MP-C, and 25km for MP-G and SP. In practical terms, although there is no improvement in performance by further increasing Q_c at the lowest lengths since linear sections are the same, for example up to curve/ 10^{-1} ER comparing $Q_c = 10$ and $Q_c \gg 1$, there is a benefit to increasing coherence times as it allows much larger edge lengths at the lower ERs e.g. 150km for ER 10^{-4} .

The results of the MP-G curve in particular are interesting as it follows the behaviour of SP before the point of sharp decrease and then follows MP-C after it. To explain the behaviour of MP-G at higher Q_c , the number of links used for the GHZ state generation was recorded (Figure 9). The similar ER patterns of MP-C and MP-G for length >60 km (at $Q_c = 10$) can be explained by having similar number of links required. However, further analysis is needed to understand why

(a) $Q_c = 1$

(b) $Q_c = 2$

(c) $Q_c = 5$

(d) $Q_c = 10$

(e) $Q_c = 100$

(f) $Q_c \gg 1$

Figure 8: Sweep of Q_c parameter for 5x5 grid.

(a) $Q_c = 1$

(b) $Q_c = 10$

(c) $Q_c \gg 1$

Figure 9: Links used for different Q_c for 5x5 grid.

SP and MP-G have similar ERs. The results from the number of links used shows a similar pattern across the different Q_c where there is a constant (SP) or slightly increasing (MP-G and MP-C) number of links used until a sharp fall to zero. This sharp decrease represents the point at which repetitions start to fail and the edge length at which this point happens increases as Q_c increases. Before this point, the links used is constant for SP since it must use the same pre-calculated route path whereas it increases for MP-G and MP-C since more resources, i.e. entanglement links, are required when attempting longer paths. This is also seen in classical networks.

We also did a sweep of p_{op} as shown in Figure 10. For the $p_{op} = 0.25$, $Q_c = 1$ case the ER was too low ($< 10^{-4}$) to display any results. The results from the p_{op} sweep show a similar pattern when p_{op} is not optimal but with the curves moved a little toward the left, showing a decrease in ER for a given edge length. This is due to the entanglement link generation probability p_e decreasing as p_{op} decreases for a given edge length. If Q_c is low the shift has a much bigger effect since the range is lower indicating that operational errors are important to keep low if there is a lot of decoherence.

Finally we looked at the ER against length for larger grids (9x9, 15x15, 25x25) with $Q_c = 1$, $p_{op} = 1$, results are shown in Figure 11. As grid size increases, the ER decreases for SP and therefore if we want to achieve the same ER for a larger network using the SP protocol the repeaters must be placed closer together. However, for MP-G and MP-C, we see the same ER across the grid sizes for $p_e \gtrsim 0.63$ which may be explained by percolation theory. The independence of grid size on ER has important consequences on the repeater placement as we can achieve high ERs for users far apart due to larger grids as long as the distances between the repeaters are not more than $\approx 10km$. As with previous results, MP-C has the best performance across all grid sizes.

To summarize, overall MP-C has the best performance where repeaters can be placed further apart for a given ER, although in some cases when coherence times increase MP-G boasts a similar performance. MP-G has the next best performance however again in some cases when coherence times increase it is similar to SP. This brings about a cost implication as although SP may be worse performing, and at best the same as MP-G, since it uses a pre-calculated path it requires fewer repeaters. The relation between cost and performance will be further analysed in the next section where we will investigate the usage rates of individual repeaters.

(a) $p_{op} = 1, Q_C = 1$

(b) $p_{op} = 1, Q_C = 10$

(c) $p_{op} = 1, Q_C \gg 1$

(d) $p_{op} = 0.75, Q_C = 1$

(e) $p_{op} = 0.75, Q_C = 10$

(f) $p_{op} = 0.75, Q_C \gg 1$

(g) $p_{op} = 0.5, Q_C = 1$

(h) $p_{op} = 0.5, Q_C = 10$

(i) $p_{op} = 0.5, Q_C \gg 1$

(j) $p_{op} = 0.25, Q_C = 10$

(k) $p_{op} = 0.25, Q_C \gg 1$

Figure 10: Sweep of p_{op} parameter for 5x5 grid.

(a) SP protocol

(b) MP-G protocol

(c) MP-C protocol

Figure 11: ER against edge length for multiple grid sizes.

4.4 Repeater Usage

Looking at repeater usage provides insight into the optimal repeater placement. In this section we first look at the usage in the 5x5 grid at different lengths and then we extend this to larger grid sizes.

4.4.1 Method

A repeater is counted as used when it has performed entanglement swapping to successfully create the GHZ state. Due to differences in protocols, the method to count usage is the same for SP and MP-G, and different for MP-C.

For SP and MP-G, repeater nodes use entanglement swapping when they create the Bell pair between the central and corner nodes. These nodes are saved and discarded after Q_c timeslots so that only the nodes that have been used to generate entanglement successfully are counted. To illustrate this an example of a successful repetition, where the GHZ state has been successfully generated, of the MP-G protocol is shown in Figure 12. At the end of the repetition the intermediate nodes in the green paths are recorded as used whereas the ones in the red path have not been since that path is discarded.

For the MP-C protocol, to compare with the SP and MP-G protocols, we first count only the nodes that perform entanglement swapping. However since any repeater node may also use fusion to create the GHZ state, compared with only the central node in SP and MP-G, we may also count a repeater as being used if it has performed entanglement swapping or fusion. To illustrate this, an example of a successful repetition is shown in Figure 13. All nodes in the Steiner tree under the green path that performs entanglement swapping are recorded as used whereas nodes that perform fusion can optionally be counted as used or not.

After all repetitions are complete the usage count for each repeater is divided by the number of repetitions to calculate a usage fraction. This fraction represents the average number of times a repeater gets used, i.e. performs entanglement swapping, for successful GHZ generation. For SP and MP-C, the usage fraction has the range $[0, 1]$ where 0 signifies that the repeater has not been used at all and 1 would mean that the repeater gets used every repetition. For MP-G, the usage fraction has the range $[0, \min(x, y)]$ where $x = \text{floor}(\text{nodal degree}/2) \times Q_c$ and $y = \text{users} - 1$. To understand the maximum end of the range for MP-G, the y is the absolute maximum where a repeater could have technically been used to create every Bell pair required. For example, for 5 users the number of Bell pairs required to create the GHZ_5 state is 4. However, this would take multiple timeslots and if Q_c is low then the maximum

Figure 12: Example simulation for 5x5 grid where $Q_c = 2$ using MP-G. Entanglement links have been created between the central and all four corner nodes using the paths indicated with red and green lines. The age of the paths represent the number of timeslots that since the entanglement link was created. As the red path's age $\geq Q_c$ it has decohered and would not be used for the GHZ state creation. On the other hand, the green paths have been used for successful GHZ state creation and thus the repeater nodes have been counted as used as shown by the +1 next to the nodes.

Figure 13: Example simulation for 5x5 grid using MP-C. The green line shows the path of the Steiner tree created. The repeater nodes within the path have been counted as shown by the +1 besides the nodes. The nodes with a +1? are counted optionally as they perform fusion rather than entanglement swapping.

may be lower. This is because the Bell pair that the repeater created would have decohered as shown in Figure 12. For example, if a node has four edges, i.e. its nodal degree, then it can perform entanglement swapping a maximum of two times within one timeslot. In reality, we see the maximum usage fraction rarely exceeding 1.

4.4.2 Results and Discussion

For all the following results, a Monte Carlo simulation was used where it was ran for 1000 repetitions with 5000 timeslots for each repetition. The number of repetitions and timeslots were able to be increased since only one network is chosen for each figure and therefore reducing the time taken to run all the simulations.

The usage was evaluated for each protocol (SP, MP-G, MP-C) for a 5x5 grid with 5 users where $Q_c = 1$ and $p_{op} = 1$. The results are shown in Figures 14 to 17. The edge lengths of 1km ($p_{ph} = 0.96$, $p_e = 0.96$), 10km ($p_{ph} = 0.63$, $p_e = 0.63$), and 20km ($p_{ph} = 0.40$, $p_e = 0.40$) were chosen as these correspond to the range of ERs seen in the previous results. Similar results are seen for higher Q_c at larger lengths, please see Appendix B for an example of this. Furthermore, see Appendix C for results for MP-C where only the repeaters that perform fusion are counted as being used.

For SP, as expected, the usage fraction of all the repeaters on the calculated path is equal and reduces as the edge length increases noting that where the usage fraction < 1 represents that on some repetitions, entanglement generation was unsuccessful. For MP-G, at length 1km, it has a pattern similar to the SP calculated path and becomes more symmetrical as edge length increases with the repeaters furthest away from the users being used less. At 1km p_e is very high (0.96) so we would expect that there are multiple entanglement paths MP-G could choose from which is why the pattern tends towards SP, the shortest path found. It is interesting to note that the nodes around the central node sometimes have a fraction > 1 . For example all the adjacent nodes to the centre node in Figure 15b. This represents multiple usages per repetition. For MP-C, a similar trend occurs as with MP-G where at length 1km there is a clear pattern that has emerged and as the length increases the pattern is lost.

The simulation was repeated for larger grid sizes (9x9, 15x15, 25x25) for each protocol shown in Figures 18 to 20. Results for MP-C which only count nodes that perform entanglement swapping as used are shown in appendix D. This was done for an edge length of 1km ($p_{ph} = 0.96$, $p_e = 0.96$) however similar results are seen as above when p_e is lowered, for example through increasing the edge length

(a) Length = 1km

(a) Length = 1km

(b) Length = 10km

(b) Length = 10km

(c) Length = 20km

(c) Length = 20km

Figure 14: Usage in 5x5 grid for the SP protocol.

Figure 15: Usage in 5x5 grid for the MP-G protocol.

(a) Length = 1km

(a) Length = 1km

(b) Length = 10km

(b) Length = 10km

(c) Length = 20km

(c) Length = 20km

Figure 16: Usage in 5x5 grid for the MP-C protocol.

Figure 17: Usage in 5x5 grid for the MP-C protocol including fusion.

or decreasing p_{op} . Examples of both are shown in Figure 21 which are further provided in Appendices E and F. For the larger grids, similar results are seen where MP-G and MP-C have defined patterns which become more symmetrical as p_e is decreased. Furthermore, as grid size increases, a larger proportion of repeaters are used minimally or not at all. We aim to explore the potential cost benefit to removing these repeaters and how it affects performance in the next section.

4.5 Removing Repeaters

By removing the least used repeaters from a network we can study how this will affect overall performance of the network by recalculating the ERs. The new network configurations are then tested at different edge lengths and then this methodology is extended to larger grids.

4.5.1 Method

Removing repeaters from a given network is achieved by deleting the nodes, which includes the edges that connect them, from the network. This models the situation of the repeater stations not being built in a given placement and therefore it also removes the entanglement distribution component described in Section 2.2.1 which is represented by the edges where entanglement links are formed. An example is shown in Figure 22 where if the nodes have a usage fraction less than a chosen minimum usage fraction they are removed. The resulting network graph state is then reset, which removes any entanglement links and usage counts, for its ER to be calculated. The minimum usage fraction was varied from 0 to 0.3 to change the number of repeaters removed. Then, the relationship between ER and edge length was found for five networks with the number of removed repeaters varied across the given range found previously.

4.5.2 Results and Discussion

The ER results from removing repeaters in the 5x5 grid (at 1km, $p_{ph} = 0.96$, $p_e = 0.96$) for MP-G and MP-C are shown in Figures 23 and 24 respectively. For each minimum usage fraction chosen the simulation was ran 1000 times with 5000 timesteps and for each edge length chosen the simulation was ran for 200 times with 1000 timesteps. The results are based off the usages results from Figure 15a for MP-G and Figure 17a for MP-C, which is how we derive the base ER. The MP-C usage results used includes fusion because we want to remove repeaters based off their total usage.

(a) 9x9

(b) 15x15

(c) 25x25

Figure 18: Usage at larger grid sizes for the SP protocol.

(a) 9x9

(b) 15x15

(c) 25x25

Figure 19: Usage at larger grid sizes for the MP-G protocol.

(a) 9x9

(b) 15x15

(c) 25x25

Figure 20: Usage at larger grid sizes for the MP-C protocol including fusion.

(a) Usage for MP-C at edge length of 10km ($p_e = 0.63$)

(b) Usage for MP-G at $p_{op} = 0.6$ ($p_e = 0.57$)

Figure 21: Examples of how usage results change as p_e changes through changing edge length (a) or operation probability (b)

Figure 22: Removal of repeater nodes from 5x5 grid based on MPG usage results from 15a

(a) ER against minimum usage fraction

(b) ER against edge length

Figure 23: ER of 5x5 grid with removed repeaters for the MP-G protocol.

Figure 24: ER of 5x5 grid with removed repeaters for the MP-C protocol.

As expected, for MP-G, as repeaters are removed the ER decreases and then has the same performance as SP once all possible 8 repeaters (32% of the total number of repeaters) are removed since it uses the same route as SP. Similar results happen for MP-C, however the total repeaters we can remove is greater (40% of the total number of repeaters) whilst still having slightly better ER results than SP and MP-G. Furthermore, we are able to remove 7 repeaters (28%) using MP-C whilst having a similar ER (0.8 GHz_s/T_{slot}) to MP-G with all repeaters although this reduces to 5 repeaters (20%) across all edge lengths.

This was repeated for the larger grids (9x9, 15x15, 25x25) as shown in Figures 25 and 26. For larger grids, relatively more repeaters can be removed. For example, for MP-G, in Figure 25e 326 repeaters (52%) can be removed whilst maintaining a similar ER of around 0.8 at edge length 1km compared with the 11 removed in the 9x9 grid (14%). For MP-C, 412 repeaters (67%) can be removed for an ER > 0.8. However, the ERs do drop more as lengths increase which may be mitigated if we look at the results for repeater usage for different lengths in order to identify and remove only the repeaters that have low usage in all cases. Furthermore, these results only apply for the specific location of users, if we change the location of users we would expect a different set of repeaters to be used less. This is indicated by the results of the previous section where usage fraction of repeaters increase when closer to a user. Therefore, these results have more pronounced implications for applications that do not require user locations to change such as clock synchronization in quantum sensing [8].

(a) 9x9: ER against minimum usage fraction

(b) 9x9: ER against edge length

(c) 15x15: ER against minimum usage fraction

(d) 15x15: ER against edge length

(e) 25x25: ER against minimum usage fraction

(f) 25x25: ER against edge length

Figure 25: ER of multiple grid sizes with removed repeaters for the MP-G protocol.

(a) 9x9: ER against minimum usage fraction

(b) 9x9: ER against edge length

(c) 15x15: ER against minimum usage fraction

(d) 15x15: ER against edge length

(e) 25x25: ER against minimum usage fraction

(f) 25x25: ER against edge length

Figure 26: ER of multiple grid sizes with removed repeaters for the MP-C protocol.

5 Conclusion

This project analysed the impact of repeater placement on multipartite state distribution in quantum networks, which is an area not studied previously. We first varied the distance between repeaters in a network. Then we measured the average number of times a repeater is used for successful multipartite generation. Finally, the repeaters that were found to be used the least were removed from the network. Throughout this, the performance of the multipartite entanglement distribution protocols, SP, MP-G, and MP-C were compared.

The results showed that overall MP-C had the best performance, where for a given entanglement rate repeaters can be placed further apart compared with SP and MP-G. We also found that entanglement rates reduce for lower operation probabilities or coherence times. However, high operational errors may be mitigated if there is low decoherence. Furthermore, the results from repeater usage gives us insight into the optimal placement of repeaters as many repeaters within the network had small relative usage. This is in particular significant for larger grid sizes where we demonstrated that more than half of repeaters in a network could be removed whilst maintaining a high ER for small edge lengths.

The methodology of analysing repeater usage to influence repeater placement in quantum networks has not been done before. As real networks have more complex structures, a promising avenue for further work would be to apply this methodology to topologies based on real-world optical networks. This will further aid the work to establish networks of quantum repeaters for long distance quantum communication.

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A Link to git repository of code

The code used in this project may be accessed through the following link: https://github.com/natashasiow/quantum_repeater

B Usage at higher Q_c

Usage results for a 5x5 grid with 5 users (corner and central nodes) where $Q_c = 10$ and $p_{op} = 1$ is shown in Figure 27 to 30.

C Fusion only usage results

Counting only fusion for when a repeater node is used in the MP-C protocol was evaluated for a 5x5 grid where $Q_c = 1$ and $p_{op} = 1$. The results are shown below in Figure 31.

D Usage for MP-C without fusion for larger grids

Usage results (only entanglement swapping) for the MP-C protocol at larger grid sizes and at edge length 1km are shown in Figure 32.

E Usage at increased lengths for larger grids

An example of how increasing edge length to 10km affects the usage results for MP-C at larger grid sizes. The results (where usage includes fusion) is shown in Figure 33.

F Usage at lower p_{op}

Figure 34 shows the sweep of the p_{op} parameter which was done for the 25x25 grid for the MP-G protocol to show how the pattern from the usage results at $p_{op} = 1$ (see Figure 19c) changes to that of $p_{op} = 0.6$ (see Figure 21b).

(a) Length = 1km

(a) Length = 1km

(b) Length = 40km

(b) Length = 40km

(c) Length = 60km

(c) Length = 60km

Figure 27: Usage in 5x5 grid for the SP protocol where $Q_c = 10$.

Figure 28: Usage in 5x5 grid for the MP-G protocol where $Q_c = 10$.

(a) Length = 1km

(b) Length = 40km

(c) Length = 60km

(a) Length = 1km

(b) Length = 40km

(c) Length = 60km

Figure 29: Usage in 5x5 grid for the MP-C protocol where $Q_c = 10$.

Figure 30: Usage in 5x5 grid for the MP-C protocol (including fusion) where $Q_c = 10$.

(a) Length = 1km

(b) Length = 10km

(c) Length = 20km

Figure 31: Usage (only fusion) in 5x5 grid for the MP-C protocol.

(a) 9x9

(b) 15x15

(c) 25x25

Figure 32: Usage at larger grid sizes for the MP-C protocol.

(a) 9x9

(b) 15x15

(c) 25x25

Figure 33: Usage at larger grid sizes with edge length of 10km for the MP-C protocol (including fusion).

Figure 34: Sweep of p_{op} parameter for MP-G 25x25 grid.